

A Study on Financial Performance of Bharath Limited, Dalmiapuram, Ariyalur

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Abstract

The financial statements are helpful to executives to assets the implications of their decisions, valuate and review their performance and implement corrective action. In fact the financial statements render invaluable service to wonder, employees, customer, suppliers and the government in their respective fields of interest. It's to be mentioned that mere presentation of statements does not serve any purpose to any of the parties mentioned above. The financial statements are useful and meaningful only when they acre analysis and interpreted. Scientific method has to adapt to analysis and interprets these statements as done in the statement is called interpretation. Some people call it 'examination; 'criticism; or 'analyses. Therefore it is meaningful to call it 'analysis and interpretation'

Introduction

Financial statements provide meaningful, useful and valuable information periodically regarding financial position and future prospects of the business concern. Various parries interpretation. Financial statement are prepared to review the state of investment in a business and result achieved the during the specific period. They reflect regard and facts accounting conventions and personal judgments.

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First Credits to Dalmia Cements

- First to install 259 TPD semi dry process kiln in India.
- First to install 500 TPD wet process kiln in India
- First to install the unique coal slurry based vertical shaft kiln technology in the world.
- First to introduce the vertical roller mill technology in India cement industry thus saving valuable energy
- First to install captive power generator in India which can run on heavy fuel oil, thus saving scarce and valuable light distillates like diesel.
- First to produce OWC in India to API specification. This unit is a pioneer in manufacturer of oil well cement conforming to specification of American petroleum institute
- First cement plant in tamilnadu to venture in mind mill farm
- First cement plant in south India to obtain the ISO9002 quality system certification in 1993. Now switched over to IS: ISO 9001-2000 VERSION.
- First unit in India to go in for vertical roller mill for cement grinding in 1997.
- First to install modern pre-calcinatory dry process kiln in this state in 1987.
- First to introduce auto kiln control system using linkman in India in 1992.replaced by RAMCO system in the year1999.

Objective of the Study

- To measure the liquidity, solvency, activity and profitability of the Dalmia Cement Bharat Ltd.,
- To analyze the funds flow statements to examine the efficiency of the corporation in managing its working capital.

Scope of the Study

- This study help to calculate the value of difference to be carried out for ratio analysis and also to calculate the value of different assets and liabilities to be carried out for comparative and common size balance sheet of different years.
- The study helps to find out resources for further development of the company.

Comparative Statement

This is yet another technique is used in financial statement analysis. These statements summarize and present related data for a numbers of years, incorporating there in changes in individual item of the financial statement. These statements help in making inter-period and inter –firm comparison and also highlight the trends in performance efficiency, and finical position. This statement normally comprises the following statements.

- Balance sheet ,Profit and loss account

Research Methodology

Research methodology is way systematically solves the research problem. Its explains various steps that are generally adopted by the researchers studying the research problem along with the logically behind them.

Research Design

Research design is purely and framework or plan for a study that guide in the collection and analysis of the data. The financial recorded we have adopted the exploratory design in collective and analyzing the data.

Research Methodology

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Data Collection

Secondary data

The financial performance of the company is analyzed by the secondary data collected. The has been collected already by someone else and which have already passed through the statistical process. In the study secondary data was pertained from articles various magazine, research books and various journals and also from company website .The data from reports have been analyzed using various tools and techniques with view to evaluate the performance in management of financial performance .The type of information collected are:

- Company history & its operations
- Company 's financial performance situation

It has been collected already by someone else who has already passed through the statistical process. The data from reports have been analyzed using various tools and techniques with the view to evaluate the performance in management of financial of statement. The data collected from various.

- Balance sheet
- Company's website
- Journals
- Magazines

Limitation of the Study

- The study is based mainly on the annual published reports of the corporation which is true only for the last day of the accounting year and it may not be relevant for the remaining part of the year.
- The study does not consider the quality made of service by the corporation which also plays a significant role in the development of the corporation.

Ratio Analysis

Ratio analysis is helpful to management and outsiders to diagnose the financial health of a business concern. Its helps in measuring the profitability, solvency, a and activity of firm. Generally ratios are used for the purpose of assessing the profitability, activity or operating efficiency and financial position of the concern. Based on the purpose the ratios are classified as follows.

Review of Literature

- The 'Financial Statement' refers to formal and original statement prepared by a business concern to disclose its financial information. AICPA (American Institute of Certified Public Accountant) says "Financial Statement are prepared for the purpose of presenting the periodical review or report on the progress by the management and deal with (I) the statement in the business and (II) the result achieved during the period of under review".
- In the words of Hampton J.J. "The Statement disclosing status of investment is knowing us balance sheet showing the result is known as profit and loss account". Thus, the term financial statement has been widely used to represent two statements prepared by accountants at the end of specific period. They are: (i) profit and loss account or income statement: and (ii) balance sheet or statement of financial position. Of late, another statement is also being prepared called 'surplus statement' or 'retained earnings statements'.

Net Profit Ratio

Net Profit Ratio

This ratio indicates what portion of sales is left to the firm after all costs.

$$\text{Net profit ratio} = \frac{\text{net profit}}{\text{Sales}} \times 100$$

Comparative Balance Sheet
Comparative Balance Sheet for the Year Ended (2016-2017)

(Rs. In Lakhs)				
Particulars	2011	2012	+ or -	%
Current Assets				
Inventories	17439.92	14456.9	-3019.08	-17.25
Sundry Debtors	2563.54	2345.75	-511.04	-17.90
Cash and Bank Balance	2524.66	2564.63	15.88	0.74
Loan and Advance	31256.80	4456.25	-152.04	-4.09
Total Current Assets(1)	26128.18	22578.90	-3666.28	-14.00
Fixed Assets				
Gross Block	70256.68	70356.91	-19.77	-0.02
Less Depreciation	29213.5	32287.40	3044.24	10.42
Net Block	41162.52	38099.51	-3064.01	-7.44
Capital work in progress	414563.43	26.63	-269.20	-19.75
Total fixed Assets(2)	7584.36	38126.14	-3360.29	-8.09
Investment (3)	108.22	14884.35	7300.29	96.27
Deferred Revenue Exp.(4)	75860.19	298.65	190.43	175.96
Total Assets (1+2+3+4)	75360.19	75825.04	190.43	175.96
Liability				
Current Liability	5658.47	4736.45	-920.02	-16.26
Provisions	2647.94	2912.6	297.14	11.35
Total Current Liability(1)	8216.39	7648.51	-622.88	-17.53
Loan Fund				
Secured loan	25221.28	24024.28	-1197.05	-4.74

Deferred payment Liability	2033.11	32358.40	1717.14	81.63
Unsecured loans	27431.23	27838.14	517.09	1.89
Total loan funds(2)	6134.25	6147.28	16	0.26
Share Holder Funds				
Share Capital	765.16	765.16	-	-
Reserves and Surplus	38526.14	33425.98	554.6	1.68
Total share Holder fund(3)	6131.2	34191.98	854.65	1.68
Deferred tax(4)	6698.9	75825.04	464.85	0.61
Total Liability(1+2+3)	75369.19	7582.01	464.85	0.61

Comparative Balance Sheet for the year ended (2017-2018)

(Rs. In Lakhs)				
Particulars	2015	2016	+ or -	%
Current Assets				
Inventories	16	19	29	1
Sundry Debtors	26	15	25	9
Cash and Bank Balance	27	22	-	-
Loan and Advance	54	99	44	8
Total Current Assets(1)	27	63	94	3
Fixed Assets				
Gross Block	70	12	64	1
Less Depreciation	59	23	-	9
Net Block	64	98	35	-
Capital work in progress	45	74	21	2
Total fixed Assets(2)	63	95	25	6
Investment (3)	74	35	-	-
Deferred Revenue Exp.(4)	98	15	-	-
Total Assets (1+2+3+4)	78	85	25	3
Liability				
Current Liability	60	12	61	1
Provisions	33	13	-	-
Total Current Liability(1)	94	15	60	6
Loan Fund				
Secured loan	23	44	21	8
Deferred payment Liability	16	59	-	-
Unsecured loans	45	78	50	1
Total loan funds(2)	34	64	21	6
Share Holder Funds				
Share Capital	-	76	-	-

Reserves and Surplus	96	75	91	2
Total share Holder fund(3)	75	35	2	2
Deferred tax(4)	32	65	45	3
Total Liability(1+2+3)	10	14	34	3

Findings and Suggestions

Findings

- The thumb rule of current ratio is 2:1. The current ratio company is fluctuations in between the 2, 89:1 .So the short –term solvency position of the company is good.
- The proprietary ratio for the 5 years from 2008-2009 to 2012-2013 were less than 0.5 that means less than 50 %.It indicates that for every Rs.1 there was an owner’s position of less than 0.50.paise.
- The quick ratios found satisfactory so the company shows good position for five years.
- The fixed assets to long term fund ratio should not become then 1. During the study period it was lies between 1.51:1 times

Suggestion

- While comparing the equity debt for the concern is little bit higher. Debt increases both the profit as well as risk. So the concern should also try to collect funds through shares within some intervals.
- The earnings per share in the present structure are also good. The company should maintain also and taken care while rising funds through various sources